

HadISDH.marine Update Document

Kate Willett (MOHC), 12th December 2023

General Notes:

The HadISDH.marine.1.5.0.2022f contains all 12 months of 2022. There are no major changes (X). A bug within the gridding code for HadISDH.marine has been detected and fixed.

The assigning of observations to gridboxes had an indexing error and an error related to the use of `int()` instead of `np.floor()`. This was putting Southern and Western Hemisphere observations with a latitude/longitude precision of .0, and all Northern and Eastern Hemisphere observations, in the 1x1 degree gridbox to the south/west.

The final gridded HadISDH product is at 5x5 degree resolution so the impact of this is dampened to a large degree by averaging over the 5x5 degree box. Differences between the older v.1.4.1.2022f and the now fixed v1.5.0.2022f are negligible in terms of large scale means and long-term trends.

However, at smaller scales and over shorter time periods, differences are detectable. Changes to the observations contributing to each 5x5 gridbox changes will directly change both the spatial coverage and gridbox mean values. This will also affect the climatological gridbox values and spatial coverage of the climatology fields which may then change the results of the quality control tests based on climatology. Some observations will be gained - where they now either pass the climatology outlier test and if there is now a climatological value for their respective gridbox where there wasn't previously. The opposite is also true, leading to further changes to the observations contributing the final 5x5 degree gridbox mean values.

Although this change is a bug fix I have classed this as a minor change (Y) in the version numbering because of the nature of the bug fix. Although the overall impact is negligible in terms of what the dataset tells us about our changing climate, it is clear that the fixed methodology has led to small changes over time and space, including spatial coverage.

Keep up to date with subsequent changes and analyses at <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/05/2022-ipdate-from-hadisdhmarinev1402022f.html>, <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/07/2022-update-from-hadisdhmarine1412022f.html> and <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/12/another-2022-update-from.html>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

1.5.0.2022f

Major Changes X:

- None

Minor Changes Y:

- A bug fix to change `int()` to `np.floor()` and correct the indexing within the gridding code.

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2022-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): [10.5281/zenodo.7357310](https://zenodo.org/record/7357310)

Reference: No change

- Willett, K. M., Dunn, R. J. H., Kennedy, J. J., and Berry, D. I. 2020: Development of the HadISDH marine humidity climate monitoring dataset. Earth System Science Data. 12,

2853-2880, doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2853-2020.

- Freeman, E., S.D. Woodruff, S.J. Worley, S.J. Lubker, E.C. Kent, W.E. Angel, D.I. Berry, P. Brohan, R. Eastman, L. Gates, W. Gloeden, Z. Ji, J. Lawrimore, N.A. Rayner, G. Rosenhagen, and S. R. Smith, 2016: ICOADS Release 3.0: A major update to the historical marine climate record. Int. J. Climatol. (doi:10.1002/joc.4775).

Other notes: The HadISDH update/analyses blog is here:

<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/05/2022-ipdate-from-hadisdhmarinev1402022f.html>,
<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/07/2022-update-from-hadisdhmarine1412022f.html> and
<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2023/12/another-2022-update-from.html>.